

Analyses of some selected physicochemical parameters of Hooghly river – A tributary of Ganga and influence of high and low tides

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Manuscript received 27 July 2016, accepted 14 September 2016

Abstract : A study was conducted to assess the water quality of a 45 km stretch of river Hooghly by measuring various physicochemical parameters and an effort has been also taken to analyse the tidal impact on river. Nine sampling stations were selected for collecting the water samples, depending on location of point sources of discharging waste. The parameters included pH, turbidity, chloride, calcium, magnesium, total hardness, total suspended solid, total dissolved solid, chemical oxygen demand (COD), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and analyzed between May 2013 to April 2014. The statistical analysis was performed on all data in the present study using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 17. The results indicate that the quality of water varies considerably from location to location. All the parameters except pH have their significance factor less than 0.001 and hence can be concluded that they are significant. From the study, it might be concluded that scattered changes of parameters in different stations was due to intrusion of waste water at different points. The tidal influence on the water quality was also explained.

Keywords : Hooghly river, physicochemical parameters, tide.

Introduction

Hooghly river also known as Bhagirathi-Hooghly is tributary of the river Ganga. The river is considered as lifeline for the people living in West Bengal. During flowing through West Bengal, the river receives both the industrial and domestic effluents as the biggest industrial and densely populated areas are located beside the river Hooghly¹. Water qualities of the River Ganga from Swarupganj to Barrackpore (in West Bengal) was determined by Mukherjee *et al.*², and compared with the values reported by the National Environmental Engineering Research Institute of India for the periods 1972-74 and 1979-80. A study by Joshi *et al.*³, reported that the water quality of River Ganga in Haridwar District in the year 2007 was better than in the year 2008. A study by Tiwary *et al.*⁴, on Ganga river in Bihar region in and around Patna revealed that discharge of untreated sewage into the Ganga causes the deterioration of water quality and loss of potable nature of water. Pollution of a river first influences its chemical quality and then systematically destroys

the food chain. River pollution is a global problem. In India it is reported that about 70% of the available water is polluted³. Tidal variation of physicochemical parameters in the Lower Gangetic Delta Region was revealed by Mitra *et al.*⁵. But due to lack of information on physicochemical characteristics and its tidal variation on the Hooghly river, an effort has been taken to overcome the lacunas.

Methodology :

Sampling stations : Water samples from nine different ghats (SS) of Hooghly river were collected for the study. These sampling stations are shown in Fig. 1. Station names are given below.

- (1) Budge Budge Ferry Ghat (SS1)
- (2) Garden Reach Ghat (SS2)
- (3) Princep Ghat (SS3)
- (4) Shovabazar Launch Ghat (SS4)
- (5) Bagbazar Launch Ghat (SS5)
- (6) Cossipore Ghat (SS6)

(7) Dakhineswar Ghat (SS7)

(8) Barrackpore Ferry Ghat (SS8)

(9) Naihati Ghat (SS9)

Care was taken in choosing the distances between each sampling station as the maximum mixing of the waste discharge with the river water was ensured.

and were completed by 10.00 hrs. The samples were collected in the first week of every month. To document tidal variations, water samples were collected both during high and low tide. Samples were collected at about 15 cm depth using the dip and grab sampling method for avoiding floating material and stored in clean polythene bottles at 4 °C⁶.

Fig. 1. Sampling stations.

Sampling program : Various physicochemical parameters studied for water quality assessment of river Hooghly were pH, turbidity, chloride, calcium, magnesium, total hardness, total suspended solid (TSS), total dissolved solid (TDS), chemical oxygen demand (COD), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD). Samples were collected from all the sampling stations between May 2013 to April 2014. Samplings commenced in the morning at about 7.00 hrs

Analysis of the water samples were done according to the Standard Methods⁷.

Statistical analysis : The statistical analysis was performed on all data in the present study using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 17 and one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) has been used to statistically analyze 10 parameters at nine locations. Inde-

Table 1. Physicochemical variables of Hooghly river water at high tide condition

Sl. Parameters No.	Sampling stations									
	SS1	SS2	SS3	SS4	SS5	SS6	SS7	SS8	SS9	SS9
1. pH	7.37±0.36	7.60±0.33	8.03±0.80	7.50±0.43	7.39±0.36	7.26±0.41	7.36±0.45	7.79±0.62	7.63±0.52	7.63±0.52
2. Turbidity (NTU)	28.67±1.87	26.17±2.08	28.17±1.80	31.50±2.61	31.58±2.94	28.67±2.64	26.50±2.20	23.50±1.68	32.58±6.33	32.58±6.33
3. Chloride (mg/L)	126.53±2.43	128.03±2.65	80.53±15.88	153.75±28.85	116.07±12.48	128.53±4.93	110.58±14.99	118.54±14.69	78.50±12.04	78.50±12.04
4. Calcium (mg/L)	40.07±1.65	49.70±3.55	40.08±5.10	48.05±4.66	38.49±3.04	36.83±3.03	33.66±3.58	37.65±2.71	30.42±1.72	30.42±1.72
5. Magnesium (mg/L)	19.20±1.74	21.12±2.44	14.39±2.47	21.10±3.40	21.12±2.09	17.25±2.01	12.50±1.98	16.40±1.63	19.65±3.82	19.65±3.82
6. Total hardness (mg/L)	180.50±18.05	212.25±17.99	160.83±32.60	208.08±27.11	184.25±22.75	164.17±15.96	136.08±24.71	162.08±15.26	158.08±10.66	158.08±10.66
7. Total suspended solid (mg/L)	230±17.58	260.83±25.75	232.50±25.98	280.00±41.12	328.33±52.87	320.33±47.38	380.08±42.06	280.33±63.17	265.67±38.28	265.67±38.28
8. Total dissolved solid (mg/L)	280±20.45	360.83±43.16	326.67±26.74	368.33±53.74	365.83±64.03	386.08±50.01	428.00±34.12	320.33±42.74	358.33±41.52	358.33±41.52
9. COD (mg/L)	19.75±2.47	19.76±2.46	24.73±4.27	29.67±5.19	29.67±4.85	39.58±5.74	39.50±5.13	29.69±7.29	29.65±7.37	29.65±7.37
10. BOD (mg/L)	6.04±1.29	5.00±1.11	6.04±1.64	8.00±1.26	8.08±1.62	10.08±2.02	10.00±1.95	6.03±1.28	8.03±1.30	8.03±1.30

Table 2. Physicochemical variables of Hooghly river water at low tide condition

Sl. Parameters No.	Sampling stations								
	SS1	SS2	SS3	SS4	SS5	SS6	SS7	SS8	SS9
1. pH	7.13±0.71	7.58±0.73	7.67±0.69	7.13±0.68	7.13±0.68	7.13±0.80	7.08±0.76	7.67±0.72	7.25±0.45
2. Turbidity (NTU)	36.50±5.95	32.50±3.53	36.75±3.91	36.25±3.60	36.83±3.83	35.00±3.02	38.58±3.37	28.63±6.36	36.25±3.14
3. Chloride (mg/L)	80.58±11.22	112.58±24.46	62.52±7.78	126.00±24.71	80.08±14.18	110.25±15.63	90.00±9.28	80.08±10.13	56.08±5.70
4. Calcium (mg/L)	56.08±6.10	59.33±4.01	41.67±8.24	60.92±7.13	54.75±4.41	49.67±4.69	40.88±5.25	42.50±4.27	36.08±3.70
5. Magnesium (mg/L)	22.08±3.20	22.08±2.87	18.33±1.72	25.92±2.84	23.00±1.76	20.67±2.02	15.83±3.30	19.25±2.01	22.08±1.68
6. Total hardness (mg/L)	232.50±27.34	240.00±26.29	180.00±36.93	260.83±53.34	236.08±35.37	210.08±17.22	168.33±22.09	186.00±22.06	182.08±21.89
7. Total suspended solid (mg/L)	280.08±47.58	312.00±36.03	286.42±28.97	352.17±54.68	352.08±55.33	352.50±54.50	460.25±42.13	310.00±22.86	310.00±22.86
8. Total dissolved solid (mg/L)	378.17±37.43	386.08±38.54	360.00±32.82	418.08±45.05	418.17±44.16	418.25±44.63	478.33±38.34	365.00±51.83	416.25±48.20
9. COD (mg/L)	29.69±7.19	24.69±4.18	39.58±4.14	39.50±4.20	39.54±3.94	44.50±5.33	49.33±5.14	34.50±3.66	29.67±3.37
10. BOD (mg/L)	8.03±0.89	7.03±0.62	10.04±1.63	12.04±1.98	12.00±2.35	12.04±2.22	15.08±2.75	8.00±0.80	10.08±2.72

pendent sample 't' test was done to find out significant difference of parameters during high and low tide. The correlation coefficients between the parameters were done.

Results and discussion

Water quality assessment of about 45 km stretch of river Hooghly was undertaken in terms of various physicochemical parameters. Results (Mean \pm SD) of physicochemical analysis of Hooghly river water at high and low tide condition are shown at Tables 1 and 2. Chemical data were analyzed by one way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) to examine the differences between group means (such as "variation" among and between groups) along the river. In the present study, results of the nine specific locations, lying over a river stretch were analyzed to find the significance of the assessed parameters based on the distance between 2 consecutive points and shown in Tables 3 and 4. Table 5 shows the difference of physicochemical variables of Hooghly river water between high and low tide

conditions. Correlations were also developed to find the relation between the parameters (Tables 6 and 7).

The reported values refer to the mean \pm SD value of water samples collected from nine different areas along the stretch of Ganga river. The results indicate that the quality of water varies considerably from location to location. All the parameters except pH have their significance factor less than 0.001 and hence can be concluded that they are significant.

pH : Small changes of pH in water quality was observed in different sampling stations. The results also showed that the river water at all the nine stations was slightly alkaline in nature.

Several authors have observed alkaline pH values in the riverine systems⁸⁻¹⁰. No significant difference was observed in pH of Hooghly river water between high and low tide condition, though pH values were high in all stations during high tide than low tide. The relatively higher

Table 3. Difference of physicochemical variables between different stations during high tide condition using ANOVA

Sl. No.	Parameters		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1.	pH	Between groups	5.727	8	0.716	2.914	0.006
2.	Turbidity (NTU)	Between groups	836.574	8	104.572	11.587	0.000
3.	Chloride (mg/L)	Between groups	54440.536	8	6805.067	32.875	0.000
4.	Calcium (mg/L)	Between groups	3671.675	8	458.959	39.475	0.000
5.	Magnesium (mg/L)	Between groups	954.407	8	119.301	19.082	0.000
6.	Total hardness (mg/L)	Between groups	58501.352	8	7312.669	15.757	0.000
7.	Total suspended solid (mg/L)	Between groups	227135.741	8	28391.968	16.375	0.000
8.	Total dissolved solid (mg/L)	Between groups	170767.074	8	21345.884	11.170	0.000
9.	COD (mg/L)	Between groups	4959.032	8	619.879	22.534	0.000
10.	BOD (mg/L)	Between groups	317.570	8	39.696	16.986	0.000

Table 4. Difference of physicochemical variables between different stations during low tide condition using ANOVA

Sl. No.	Parameters		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1.	pH	Between groups	6.250	8	0.781	1.606	0.133
2.	Turbidity (NTU)	Between groups	851.352	8	106.419	5.932	0.000
3.	Chloride (mg/L)	Between groups	52698.992	8	6587.374	28.752	0.000
4.	Calcium (mg/L)	Between groups	7935.167	8	991.896	32.710	0.000
5.	Magnesium (mg/L)	Between groups	824.000	8	103.000	17.026	0.000
6.	Total hardness (mg/L)	Between groups	103898.241	8	12987.280	13.515	0.000
7.	Total suspended solid (mg/L)	Between groups	277439.963	8	34679.995	18.287	0.000
8.	Total dissolved solid (mg/L)	Between groups	128668.407	8	16083.551	8.819	0.000
9.	COD (mg/L)	Between groups	5908.781	8	738.598	33.392	0.000
10.	BOD (mg/L)	Between groups	634.111	8	79.264	21.124	0.000

Table 5. Difference of physicochemical variables of Hooghly river water between high and low tide conditions

Sl. No.	Parameters	Significant level in different Sampling stations								
		SS1	SS2	SS3	SS4	SS5	SS6	SS7	SS8	SS9
1.	pH	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
2.	Turbidity (NTU)	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.05	NS
3.	Chloride (mg/L)	P<0.01	P<0.05	P<0.01	P<0.05	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01
4.	Calcium (mg/L)	P<0.01	P<0.01	NS	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01
5.	Magnesium (mg/L)	P<0.05	NS	P<0.01	P<0.05	P<0.05	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	NS
6.	Total hardness (mg/L)	P<0.01	P<0.01	NS	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01
7.	Total suspended solid (mg/L)	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	NS	NS	P<0.01	P<0.05	P<0.01
8.	Total dissolved solid (mg/L)	P<0.01	NS	P<0.05	P<0.05	P<0.05	NS	P<0.01	P<0.05	P<0.01
9.	COD (mg/L)	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.05	P<0.01	NS	NS
10.	BOD (mg/L)	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.05	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.05

Table 6. Correlation of physicochemical variables of Hooghly river water in high tide condition

Parameters	pH	Turbidity	Chloride	Calcium	Magnesium	Total hardness	Total suspended solid	Total dissolved solid	COD	BOD
pH	-									
Turbidity (NTU)	-0.075	-								
Chloride (mg/L)	-0.185	0.029	-							
Calcium (mg/L)	0.042	-0.079	0.537**	-						
Magnesium (mg/L)	-0.077	0.361**	0.298**	0.311**	-					
Total hardness (mg/L)	0.050	0.138	0.414**	0.594**	0.505**	-				
Total suspended solid (mg/L)	-0.205*	-0.088	0.094	-0.240*	-0.190*	-0.234*	-			
Total dissolved solid (mg/L)	-0.067	0.068	0.107	-0.089	-0.128	-0.108	0.418**	-		
COD (mg/L)	-0.183	0.011	0.023	-0.353**	-0.275**	-0.332**	0.444**	0.418**	-	
BOD (mg/L)	-0.219*	0.161	0.050	-0.334**	-0.191*	-0.331**	0.434**	0.383**		-

Table 7. Correlation of physicochemical variables of Hooghly river water in low tide condition

Parameters	pH	Turbidity	Chloride	Calcium	Magnesium	Total hardness	Total suspended solid	Total dissolved solid	COD	BOD
pH	-									
Turbidity (NTU)	0.219*	-								
Chloride (mg/L)	-0.081	-0.052	-							
Calcium (mg/L)	-0.049	-0.016	-0.535**	-						
Magnesium (mg/L)	-0.014	0.100	-0.228*	0.406**	-					
Total hardness (mg/L)	-0.030	0.025	0.419**	0.641**	0.488**	-				
Total suspended solid (mg/L)	-0.152	0.087	0.202*	-0.065	-0.190*	-0.142	-			
Total dissolved solid (mg/L)	-0.062	0.213*	0.115	-0.098	-0.070	0.099	0.466**	-		
COD (mg/L)	-0.141	0.240*	0.090	-0.161	-0.295**	-0.181	0.499**	0.338**	-	
BOD (mg/L)	-0.141	0.378**	0.102	-0.099	-0.146	-0.104	0.435**	0.367**	0.625*	-

values of pH during high tide in all the selected stations are the effect of intrusion of saline water from Bay of Bengal.

Turbidity : There are differences in turbidity among the stations. Actually, the domestic wastewater which goes through the river system may add significant quantity of

organic matter and inorganic material that contribute to turbidity. According to Unni¹¹, turbidity values increase as a consequence of the flow of rainwater carrying suspended particles and the discharge of industrial effluents. Significant increase in turbidity in all stations was observed during low tide.

Chloride : Differences in values of chloride are observed among the stations. It is to be noted that chloride content was low in SS9 i.e. Naihati Ghat during both tides. It might be due to the highest distance of SS9 station from the sea Bay of Bengal than other stations. Significant higher values of chloride for all stations were observed in high tide condition than low tide due to the intrusion of sea water in the river. Chloride showed significant positive correlation with calcium, magnesium and total hardness.

Calcium, magnesium and total hardness : Scattered changes of calcium, magnesium and total hardness in water quality were observed in different sampling stations during both tides. Tidal influence on those parameters was higher at low tide and lower at high tide. Significant tidal variation ($P < 0.01$) was observed in most of the stations.

Total Suspended Solid (TSS) and Total Dissolved Solid (TDS) : Same scattered scenario was observed in both TSS and TDS in all stations. Most of the stations showed significant higher value in TSS and TDS during low tide than high tide.

COD and BOD : The oxygen-demanding nature of biodegradable organics is of maximum importance in natural water systems. High COD and BOD values observed at different stations may be attributed to discharge of domestic wastewater in to river. Significant increase in both COD and BOD in most of all stations was observed dur-

ing low tide. It is generally seen that low tide brings more sewage from the upstream stations and increased BOD and COD values significantly than high tide condition.

Conclusion

From the above analysis, it can be concluded that scattered changes of parameters in different stations might be due to intrusion of waste water at different points. The tidal influence on the water quality was also elucidated.

References

1. D. Chakraborty and T. K. Gupta, *West Bengal Pollution Control Board*, 2003, pp. 1-19.
2. D. Mukherjee, M. Chattopadhyay and S. C. Lahiri, *Environmentalist*, 1993, **13**, 199.
3. D. M. Joshi, A. Kumar and N. Agarwal, *Rasayan Journal of Chemistry*, 2009, **2**, 195.
4. R. K. Tiwary, G. P. Rajak, Abhishek and M. R. Mondal, *J. Environ. Sci. Eng.*, 2005, **47**, 326.
5. A. Mitra, K. Mondal and K. Banerjee, *Journal of Spatial Hydrology*, 2011, **11**, 52.
6. C. B. Shivayogimath, P. B. Kalburgi, U. B. Deshannavar and D. B. M. Virupakshaiah, *I Res. J. Environment Sci.*, 2012, **1**, 12.
7. APHA, "Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Waste Water", 20th ed., American Public Health Association, Washington DC, 1998.
8. S. K. Khare and K. S. Unni, "Changes in Physico-chemical factors and distribution of periphyton in Pollar river", Proc. All India Seminar on Water Quality around urban ecosystems, ed. K. S. Unni, 1986.
9. D. K. Singh and C. P. Singh, *Ind. J. Environmental Health*, 1990, **32**, 26.
10. N. Swarnalatha and A. Narsingarao, *Indian J. Microbial Ecology*, 1992, **3**, 41.
11. K. S. Unni, *Int. Rev. Gesanten. Hydrobiol.*, 1985, **70**, 845.

